

**PERCEPTIONS OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS TOWARDS THE
EVALUATION SYSTEM**

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Abstract:

The objective of a good evaluation system must be development of students as well as teachers. Evaluation therefore must be considered as a serious activity. Most teachers consider that their jobs are over when they finish teaching. This is not so. Teachers must follow through the students during and after evaluation and provide constructive feedback for their improvement.

With these positive thoughts towards the evaluation system the researcher embarked into a study of the attitude of prospective teachers towards the evaluation system. The education system has three sets of people who must effectively interact to achieve the objectives. The paper highlights the attitudes of the prospective teachers as they see projected by teachers, students and parents.

The paper also highlights certain suggestions to make evaluation comprehensive, long lasting and transformative.

Key words: Evaluation, attitude, communication, reporting.

Introduction: Evaluation is a means to instill love for education. This is a broad minded thinking of a handful of teachers. Most teachers show aversion to the task of evaluation or consider it as an added appendage to the teaching profession. Most of the time evaluation work is taken with a feeling that it is a burden on teachers. How much joy should the teacher have in her heart when she sees the product of her work? This is the question that most teachers must reflect and find out. The generic goal of evaluation is to provide valuable feedback which will lead to growth. Moreover evaluation also leads to feedback to the teacher, appropriate decision making and policy formulation for the benefit of the students.

Rationale for the study: Teachers at the formation stage in the B.Ed. colleges are trained in evaluation in the theory papers as well as in a practical way in their internship program. During the theory classes discussions are held on effective manner of evaluation and how the attitude of the teacher must be towards the evaluation system. In spite of all this when the teachers join schools they automatically develop negative attitude. Teachers are seen talking ill about the evaluation work assigned to them and most often the focus is on the workload. It is a common feature in most educational institutions to see that teachers complain about the kind of answers that students have written in the answer papers but they do not realize that it is the reflection of their own teaching. It is with this concern in mind that the study was undertaken to find out the perceptions of the prospective teachers towards evaluation.

Scope and Delimitations of the study: The study is delimited to the B.Ed. students of one particular B.Ed. college only. The perceptions of the prospective teachers were studied before providing them any input of the theoretical background on evaluation. Thus the data collected is the true representation of their background knowledge of evaluation and the projection of their true attitude towards it.

Statement of the problem: Perceptions of prospective teachers towards evaluation system .

Operational definitions:

Perceptions: This would refer to the feelings attached to the evaluation system or evaluation work assigned to teachers in school, as well as the projected feelings of parents and school students as felt by the B.Ed. students.

Prospective teachers are the B.Ed. students included in this study.

Evaluation means all the tasks which lead to providing students the marks, feedback and reporting of their performance. It also means the entire system of evaluation existing in the school.

Aim of the study:

To study the perceptions of prospective teachers towards evaluation.

Objectives of the study:

- To classify the prospective teachers according to the levels of attitudes towards evaluation.
- To study the perceptions of the prospective teachers on projected reactions of parents towards evaluation
- To study the perceptions of the prospective teachers on projected reactions of teachers towards evaluation
- To study the perceptions of the prospective teachers on projected reactions of students towards evaluation

Significance of the study: The study will reveal the attitude of prospective teachers towards evaluation. The study is important as it would reveal all the negative aspects of the perceptions which need to be worked upon. If prospective teachers go to the schools with a negative attitude then the objectives of evaluation will not be achieved. The study would be of great help to B.Ed. colleges as it would bring out the importance of moulding prospective teachers towards positive aspects of evaluation. The tool used in the study could be used by B.Ed. colleges to understand the perceptions of B.Ed. trainees before and after the course.

Methodology used: The descriptive method was used for the study.

Tool for the study: The researcher conducted an informal interview with the B.Ed. students as a pilot run to understand the general perceptions towards evaluation and framed the statements of the tool which contained 25 statements. The statements were considered to understand the projected reactions of the teachers, students and parents as was perceived by the B.Ed. trainee through their own experience or through hearsay. This paper consists of the detailed qualitative analysis of 7 statements only. The rating scale had four options strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree.

Sample and Sampling technique: A purposive sampling was done considering the prospective teachers only B.Ed. students of one particular college were selected for this study. The final number of students who participated in the study was 94 students.

Data collection: The data were collected in a class session by properly explaining the details of the rating scale. Time was provided and students were asked to read, understand the statement and then mention their option against each statement.

Analysis of data: The data were converted to the quantitative form and a qualitative analysis was carried out with the help of percentage analysis.

The analysis of the objectives were done as follows:

- **To classify the prospective teachers according to the levels of attitudes towards evaluation.**

The calculated mean was 68. The observation of the scores states that 40% of the teachers have scored below the mean that shows a negative attitude towards evaluation. It is seen that around 30% of the teachers have scored around the mean and 30% of the teachers have very positive attitude towards evaluation.

- **To study the perceptions of the prospective teachers on projected reactions of parents towards evaluation.**

Two statements were analysed in this paper to find out the perceptions of parents towards evaluation.

The statements are as follows:

- Parents are upset with the way the teachers mark students

- Parents cannot understand the standards of the school when it comes to the evaluation system.

On analysis of these two statements it is seen that 65% of prospective teachers agree that parents are upset with the way that teachers mark the students.

It is observed that 57% of the parents according to the prospective teachers do not understand the standards of evaluation.

- **To study the perceptions of the prospective teachers on projected reactions of teachers towards evaluation.**

Three statements were analysed in this paper to find out the perceptions of teachers towards the evaluation system. The statements are as follows:

- Teachers use the evaluation system as a whip against the students.
- Teachers always grumble about corrections.
- Evaluation is the most difficult job of a teacher.

25% of prospective teachers feel that the evaluation system is used as a whip against the students.

66% of the prospective teachers find that teachers always grumble about corrections.

50% of the teachers find evaluation as the most difficult job of a teacher.

- **To study the perceptions of the prospective teachers on projected reactions of students towards evaluation.**

Two statements were analysed in this paper to understand the projected reactions of students as perceived by prospective teachers. The statements are as follows:

- The report day is a day which most students want to miss.
- Evaluation makes or breaks students.

79% of prospective teachers agree that the report day is a dreadful day for students and students want to miss it.

73% of prospective teachers think that students consider evaluation makes or breaks students.

Findings and conclusions of the study:

1. Most teachers have either average or poor attitude towards evaluation. This shows that the prospective teachers have come in with a negative attitude towards evaluation.
2. The results show that parents are not very happy, informed or involved in the evaluation system.
3. Teachers do consider evaluation as an unwelcome activity as shown in the results, which shows that most teachers grumble about evaluation and half of the prospective teachers feel that evaluation is a difficult job.
4. The projected reactions of students as perceived by prospective teachers show that students also consider the evaluation as an unpleasant activity and it will lead to either building a student or causing harm.

Suggestions arising from the study:

The results show that the projected feelings towards the activity, of evaluation on the whole do not seem very positive in nature. The B.Ed. colleges have to provide a number of experiences in order to improve the situation. A discussion on the broad objectives of evaluation and the specific objectives of each activity could provide appropriate direction to teachers towards this activity. A well designed rubric could bring clarity to teachers, students and parents on what to evaluate and how to evaluate.

Most of the time, it is inadequate communication between teachers and students that leads to the negative attitude towards evaluation. The negative attitudes are passed on from students to parents. Before any evaluative activity it is important that teachers communicate all details of testing, marking and reporting to students and parents so that they are mentally prepared for the evaluation. Teachers must be patient to clarify all doubts.

The colleges of education must train prospective teachers on effective reporting of results. Reporting of results is a responsibility that all teachers must deliver seriously. How do we report effectively in written and oral form must be a school policy to be adhered to. All teachers must be cordial in reporting. Teachers must show hope for every student be it a gifted student or a slow learner, this must be the target of all teachers in the school.

Parents are always anxious about their child. A session on how to deal with parents need to be conducted for teachers from time to time. Most of the time, the parents are not receptive to feedback. In this case parent interactions must be conducted to communicate the nuances of an effective feedback. Teachers must be open to students' point of view when it comes to feedback. Feedback as understood must not be one way but a two way channel. It is important to work on the feedback given and make changes for the student's improvement. Most evaluation stops with corrections and reporting of results but it is the follow up after evaluation that makes it effective.

Remedial instruction must be the responsibility of every school. An institution with a good backup of remedial instruction could be considered as a good institution. Teachers must not focus more on the work load but the student load after evaluation, that is more the number of students lagging behind means the teacher is lagging behind. In some schools teachers openly declare that students must go for tuitions. This is against professional ethics of a teacher.

Evaluation must also bring in a lot of self improvement in teachers. Reflective assessment is what we must aim for. Teachers must reflect on the results and work towards progress of their students. Parents are partners in the evaluation. Teachers must realize that a lot of improvement in the results can happen with parental co operation. Teachers have to consider students and parents in the journey of evaluation in order to get the best out of this activity.

A positive attitude towards evaluation leads to positive involvement of the teacher in the evaluation process. It is therefore an urgent task of all B.Ed. colleges to instill in the prospective teachers a positive attitude and openness to the task of evaluation.

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